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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR FORMING SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: The interrelationship and conceptual harmony between the notion of social responsibility and the competence of “socially active citizenship” within the primary education system are explored. Internal (personal) and external (social) factors contributing to the formation of social responsibility are analyzed, and their role in the development of students’ personalities is substantiated. Ten effective pedagogical methods for developing responsibility among primary school students (service-learning, PBL, digital citizenship, and others), as well as mechanisms for adapting them to the national context, are examined. Scientific conclusions are presented regarding the long-term positive impact of social responsibility education on social stability and the development of an active citizenship environment.

Key words: primary education, social responsibility, active citizenship competence, moral consciousness, internal and external factors, service-learning, digital citizenship, socialization, pedagogical strategy.

Annotatsiya: Boshlang'ich ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy mas'uliyat tushunchasining “ijtimoiy faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasi” bilan o'zaro aloqadorligi va mazmuniy uyg'unligi tadqiq etilgan. Ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni shakllantiruvchi ichki (shaxsiy) va tashqi (ijtimoiy) omillar tahlil qilinib, ularning o'quvchi shaxsi kamolotidagi o'rni asoslab berilgan. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida mas'uliyatni rivojlantirishning 10 ta samarali pedagogik usuli (xizmat ta'limi, PBL, raqamli fuqarolik va boshqalar) hamda ularni milliy kontekstga moslashtirish mexanizmlari yoritilgan. Yakunda ijtimoiy mas'uliyat tarbiyasining jamiyat barqarorligi va faol fuqarolik muhitini shakllantirishdagi uzoq muddatli ijobiy ta'siri yuzasidan ilmiy xulosalar taqdim etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlang'ich ta'lim, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat, faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasi, axloqiy ong, ichki va tashqi omillar, xizmat ta'limi (service-learning), raqamli fuqarolik, ijtimoiylashuv, pedagogik strategiya.

Аннотация: Исследованы взаимосвязь и содержательная гармония понятия социальной ответственности с компетенцией “социально активного гражданства” в системе начального образования. Проанализированы внутренние (личностные) и внешние (социальные) факторы формирования социальной ответственности, а также обоснована их роль в развитии личности учащегося. Рассмотрены 10 эффективных педагогических методов развития ответственности у младших школьников (обучение через служение, PBL, цифровое гражданство и др.), а также механизмы их адаптации к национальному контексту. В заключение представлены выводы о долгосрочном положительном влиянии воспитания социальной ответственности на социальную стабильность и формирование среды активного гражданства.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, социальная ответственность, компетенция активного гражданства, нравственное сознание, внутренние и внешние факторы, обучение через служение (service-learning), цифровое гражданство, социализация, педагогическая стратегия.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of social responsibility is inextricably linked with the “socially active citizenship competence” defined in the general secondary education system, and these concepts complement each other in terms of content while reinforcing one another in practical application. Social responsibility includes such qualities as an individual’s awareness of duties and obligations in society, a conscious desire to fulfill them, and a willingness to take responsibility for the outcomes of actions.

This competence is manifested as a practical expression of social responsibility. Students not only acquire knowledge but also demonstrate their sense of responsibility through practical activities. Therefore, social responsibility serves as the ideological and spiritual foundation of “socially active citizenship competence”. In turn, “socially active citizenship competence” aims to develop students in general secondary education into individuals who correctly understand their rights and responsibilities, actively participate in social life, and appreciate democratic values and the rule of law. This competence is expressed as a practical manifestation

of social responsibility because students demonstrate responsibility not only through knowledge acquisition but also through practical activities. Thus, social responsibility serves as the ideological and spiritual basis of “socially active citizenship competence”, while competence itself represents a purposeful and systematic implementation of this foundation within the educational process. Such harmony ensures students’ development as mature, responsible, and active citizens who are capable of balancing personal interests with the interests of society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the process of forming social responsibility, internal (personal) and external (social) factors are interconnected and exert a harmonious influence on one another.

Internal (personal) factors include an individual’s spiritual and moral values, worldview, personal motives, emotions, and self-imposed expectations. For example, such qualities as the development of moral consciousness, a commitment to justice and fairness, conscientious fulfillment of duties, compassion, and kindness strengthen social responsibility through an individual’s internal motivation. In addition, the ability to engage in self-assessment and foresee the consequences of one’s actions plays a significant role among internal factors.

External (social) factors include an individual’s living environment, family upbringing, educational processes in schools and educational institutions, media influence, cultural traditions, and broader social influences. For example, family upbringing styles, extracurricular activities in which students participate, community-based social projects, and volunteer activities may contribute to the development of a sense of responsibility. Furthermore, programs aimed at civic education within state policy represent important external factors.

In general, through the harmony of internal and external factors, social responsibility manifests itself not only as theoretical knowledge but also as an individual’s life position and practical activities. While internal factors shape a person’s internal readiness and confidence, external factors create opportunities for applying and strengthening these qualities in real-life situations.

Table 1: Internal and External Factors Forming Social Responsibility

Factor Type	Components	Comment
Internal (personal) factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spiritual and moral values • Personal motives • Level of moral awareness • Feelings and empathy • Self-assessment 	An individual's internal motivation, moral maturity, and conscious attitude toward duty determine the fundamental internal foundations of social responsibility.
External (social) factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family education • Educational environment in educational institutions • Community activities • Media influence • Cultural traditions and customs • State civic education policy 	An individual's social environment and educational influences serve the practical formation and strengthening of social responsibility.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology was based on methods of collecting and analyzing data related to the formation of social responsibility and active citizenship competence in primary education. Data were obtained through the review of scientific literature, pedagogical studies, monographs, and contemporary educational sources addressing social responsibility, citizenship education, and pedagogical strategies. Comparative analysis and document analysis methods were used to identify existing approaches and educational practices applied in national and international contexts. The collected information was analyzed using descriptive, comparative, and synthesis methods in order to determine the common and distinctive features of various pedagogical strategies. In addition, different educational approaches and practical methods were systematically compared to evaluate their effectiveness and potential application in primary education settings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The importance of social responsibility in education is manifested primarily in ensuring the spiritual maturity of the younger generation, civic consciousness, and active participation in the life of society. It is not limited to the provision of knowledge within the educational process but also teaches students to take responsibility for their actions, understand the interests of the community and society, and adhere to legal and moral norms.

At the same time, social responsibility, as an integral component of the educational process, harmoniously develops such qualities in students as moral awareness, legal culture, civic position, and active citizenship. As a result, graduates of educational institutions develop not only as educated individuals but also as responsible citizens who understand their duty to society and are prepared to fulfill it.

The goals established for social responsibility education within the educational process constitute a systematic set of tasks aimed at ensuring the spiritual and civic maturity of the younger generation. Primarily, the goal is to develop students' ability to understand their duties and obligations and to consciously strive to fulfill them. At the same time, key objectives include understanding social norms and rules, respecting laws, and adhering to the principles of justice and fairness. Strengthening students' civic positions through educational processes and developing initiative and active citizenship that serve the interests of society and the community also represent urgent educational tasks. Moreover, by fostering feelings of compassion, kindness, environmental awareness, and cultural responsibility in children, their life position is expected to become comprehensive, responsible, and stable. Consequently, the educational process becomes not merely a means of imparting knowledge but also the primary mechanism for raising a spiritually mature, socially active, and responsible generation.

The relevance of forming social responsibility at the primary education stage is explained primarily by the fact that the developmental period from 7–10 years of age represents a stage of rapid formation of “emotional-moral sensitivity” and behavioral habits. During this period, children begin to understand the essence of rules, recognize the “I–we” relationship, and assess the consequences of their actions. Therefore, it is important to purposefully instill such qualities as moral awareness, legal culture, and empathy at an early stage. Otherwise, indifference to social norms may become firmly established.

The second aspect is that it serves as a “practical laboratory” in the socialization of primary school children. Through group games, projects, stage performances, hashar activities, and “mercy-compassion” initiatives, children practically experience collective work planning, task-sharing, turn-taking, agreement-building, and responsibility. This practical environment connects the competency-based model of education with real life: moral consciousness becomes conscious adherence to rules, civic position develops into initiative for the benefit of the community, and active citizenship transforms into voluntary participation.

The third aspect is that social responsibility within the digital environment and media education is inseparably linked with the process of digitalization. Teaching children at an early stage information selection skills, standards of moral behavior on the Internet, online safety, and communication culture establishes the foundation for future civic activity. Family–school–community cooperation is also crucial at this stage. When parental example, teacher leadership, and community support are integrated, social responsibility is strengthened not merely as knowledge but as a habit and a personal position. As a result, primary school graduates develop into active citizens who not only “know the rules” but also follow them with internal conviction while considering the interests of both the community and society.

Effective methods for developing social responsibility in both national and global educational practice are presented below. These methods are practice-oriented and are accompanied by examples and recommendations for adaptation to primary education settings.

- 1) **Service-learning and social practice.** Connecting social issues with curriculum topics and involving children in real service activities such as helping elderly people, environmental cleaning, charity events, and “kindness” visits. This method strengthens empathy, community involvement, and responsibility because knowledge is transformed into practice.

Adaptation: Application of the “One month – one service” principle; connecting lesson topics (for example, natural science) with regional improvement initiatives.

- 2) **Project-based learning (PBL) and problem-based tasks.** Children prepare socially useful group projects such as “Waste Sorting,” “Class Etiquette Rules,” and “Competent Citizen” wall newspapers. Problems are identified, solutions are planned, and results are presented publicly.

Results: Initiative, planning skills, responsibility sharing, and accountability.

- 3) **Cooperation with the community (school–family–community).** Joint activities with neighborhood councils, NGOs, libraries, museums, and theaters, including parents' days, hashar activities, and professions festivals.

Results: Development of a “me–we” perspective, prioritization of community interests, and local civic consciousness.

- 4) **Civic culture and student voice.** Activities such as class councils, mini-parliaments, “Young Leader” clubs, debates, friendly discussions, and Model UN initiatives. Children participate in creating rules and making class decisions.

Outcome: Understanding rights and responsibilities, justice and respect, and a culture of compromise.

- 5) **Mentorship and peer learning.** Older students guide and assist younger students through “supportive pair” initiatives.

Outcome: Responsibility, empathy, and discipline through personal example.

- 6) **Social-emotional learning (SEL) and tolerance exercises.** Regular activities aimed at recognizing and managing emotions, empathy development, listening skills, honest communication, and peaceful conflict resolution.

Outcome: Internal control, conscience, and readiness for moral decision-making.

- 7) **Digital citizenship and media literacy.** Online safety, information verification, cyber ethics, and responsible behavior in digital environments, including short social videos and online questionnaires.

Effect: Responsible behavior in digital environments and critical attitudes toward information.

- 8) **Ecological directions and “green school” initiatives.** Tree planting, water conservation, waste sorting, and “green days.”

Effect: Environmental responsibility and respect for common property.

- 9) **Theatrical actions and social scenarios.** Socially themed performances, role-playing games, and forum theater activities.

Effect: Experiencing moral decisions and developing humanitarian awareness.

- 10) **Restorative practices.** “Friendly circles,” “cultural conversations,” and agreements focused on compensating for harm.

Effect: Development of responsibility acceptance and correction of consequences.

The following mechanisms are recommended for supporting educational activities:

1. Integration into annual educational plans: a specific social task for each quarter.
2. Indicators and rubrics: empathy, cooperation, initiative, and conscious adherence to rules monitored through assessment criteria.
3. Portfolio and reflection: “My Duty” essays, photo reports, and reflection notebooks.
4. Communication with families: brief guidelines for parents and lists of household responsibilities.
5. Inclusiveness: assigning roles for each student and ensuring “success experiences” through small tasks.

When adapting projects to the national context, attention should be given to the following:

1. Community resources: hashar traditions, turn-taking practices, and assistance to elderly people based on traditional values.
2. “Citizenship Corner,” “Transparent Library,” and “Young Leader” initiatives as spaces for information, initiative, and accountability.
3. Bilingual (CLIL) lessons integrating social topics with foreign language learning.
4. STEAM integration: environmental projects combined with calculations and visual or video preparation.

When evaluating project outcomes:

1. Diagnostics (initial–semi-annual–final): questionnaires, observation sheets, and third-party opinions (parents and community members).
2. Dissemination of results: class conferences and project reports on school websites.
3. Long-term impact: habitual service, voluntary activity, and a sense of community belonging.

Thus, combining national (community, hashar, teacher–student interaction) and global (service-learning, SEL, restorative practices, digital citizenship) approaches elevates social responsibility from the level of knowledge to the level of personal position and everyday behavior.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The long-term impact of the formation of social responsibility is manifested primarily in the development of an individual as a fully developed personality. Social responsibility represents a set of spiritual and moral qualities that include a consciously accepted duty and commitment to fulfilling it, which subsequently becomes a permanent aspect of an individual's life. Such a person is formed not only as an individual who follows rules but also as a person capable of prioritizing the rule of law, justice, compassion, civic duty, and public interests.

At the societal level, the long-term impact of social responsibility ensures an environment of social stability, harmony, and mutual trust. A community of responsible individuals solves problems based on consensus, uses resources rationally, and takes sustainable steps toward development. At the same time, social responsibility serves as an important foundation for an active civil society. Responsible citizens are interested in public administration processes, support social initiatives, and actively participate in finding solutions to global problems. Therefore, any action aimed at developing social responsibility contributes not only to the long-term development and stability of individuals but also of society as a whole.

Overall, analyses of social responsibility indicate that it is a socio-moral category manifested through an individual's awareness of duties and responsibilities toward society, the ability to assess the consequences of actions in advance, and engagement in activities that serve social interests. While national pedagogical perspectives emphasize discipline, patriotism, justice, and cooperation, foreign scientific sources prioritize civic activity, engagement with global issues, and adherence to ethical norms.

The formation of social responsibility within the educational system, particularly at the primary education stage, represents one of the essential conditions for developing children's moral awareness, civic position, legal culture, and active citizenship. Therefore, if harmony between internal (personal) and external (social) factors is ensured within the process of social responsibility education, its effects become long-term and contribute to the development of a well-rounded individual, a stable society, and an active civic environment.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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